

Workshop on Open Citations and Open Scholarly Metadata 2022

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Authors' contribution acknowledgement

Silvio Peroni

Associate Professor in Computer Science at the [Department of Classical Philology and Italian Studies, University of Bologna](#), member of the [Digital Humanities Advanced Research Centre \(/DH.arc\)](#) and director of [OpenCitations](#) and of the [Research Centre for Open Scholarly Metadata](#).

List of the video presentations

- Zeyd Boukhers (Fraunhofer FIT, Germany). *Evaluation Scheme of FAIRness in Scholarly Data*. [\[video\]](#)
- Fabian Beck (University of Bamberg). *Assessing Discussions of Related Work through Citation-based Recommendations and Network Visualization*. [\[video\]](#)
- David Pride and Petr Knoth (KMi, The Open University). *Enriching open citation metadata with citation type classification*. [\[video\]](#)
- Muhammad Ahsan Shahid (GESIS). *OUTCITE - An integrated platform for comparing reference extraction toolkits and provisioning their output*. [\[video\]](#)
- Eric Schares (Iowa State University). *Exploring a University's Cited Reference Patterns with OpenAlex*. [\[video\]](#)
- George Macgregor (University of Strathclyde). *Enhancing discovery and enriching the scholarly graph with the Research Outputs Metadata Schema (Rioxx)*. [\[video\]](#)
- Dominika Tkaczyk (Crossref). *Things you wish you didn't have to know about metadata matching*. [\[video\]](#)
- Leyla Jael Castro (ZB MED Information Centre for Life Sciences; NFDI4DataScience consortium), Zeyd Boukhers (NFDI4DataScience

consortium), Olga Giraldo (ZB MED Information Centre for Life Sciences; NFDI4DataScience consortium), Adamantios Koumpis (Institute for Medical Informatics, University of Cologne; NFDI4DataScience consortium), Oya Beyan (Institute for Medical Informatics, University of Cologne; NFDI4DataScience consortium), Dietrich Rebholz-Schuhmann (ZB MED Information Centre for Life Sciences; Institute for Medical Informatics, University of Cologne). ***NFDI4DataScience registry for reproducible Data Science and Artificial Intelligence.*** [[video](#)]

- Kim Fidomski (Fraunhofer Institute for Applied Information Technology FIT). ***It is time for a distributed architecture for scholarly data management.*** [[video](#)]
- Bianca Kramer (Sesame Open Science), Hans de Jonge (Dutch Research Council - NWO). ***The availability of completeness of open funder metadata.*** [[video](#)]

The first video is by Zeyd from the Fraunhofer Institute for Applied Information Technology. Here, he defines a Scholarly Digital Object, which is a composed object consisting of an article describing research (identified by a PID, a persistent identifier, and with a license associated, usually provided by the publisher), accompanied by additional items such as the list of authors (all of them identified with PIDs), other metadata (e.g. the venue, the publisher of the article), the datasets and code introduced or used in the article (with their metadata), the research results, etc. Then, Zeyd quickly introduces the main issues concerning the FAIRification of a Scholarly Digital Object and concludes the speech by advertising the first conference on FAIR Digital Objects in Leiden at the end of October 2022.

In his video, Fabian, from the University of Bamberg, presents his tool for helping people in peer reviewing. Indeed, any research builds on previous works, and one of peer reviewers' activities is to identify if some relevant work has been missed from a paper. PURE Suggest is one of the tools for helping reviewers with this activity. Starting from a selection of seed works, for instance, those cited in the reference list of a given article, the tool returns other relevant works that are

related to them. In the video, Fabian shows a tutorial on how to use PURE with a real example.

In his video, David, from the Knowledge Media Institute, Open University, introduces his experience studying academic tenure practices. Often, research assessment exercises are based on metrics built upon citations that are all treated equally. However, citations may have different functions within a paper (for instance, because the citing paper reuses a method introduced in the cited work or either agrees or disagrees with the conclusions of the cited work, etc.). According to the current literature, automatic annotation (via ML tools) or manual annotation (by the authors) have been the main ways to assign such a citation function to citations. Although essential, David warns that such reasons for citing should not become a way to create new metrics but rather to understand better how a piece of work has been cited.

Muhammad, from GESIS, introduces a project, i.e. OUTCITE, which aims to develop a tool for detecting the bibliographic references in publications and matching them to existing databases. The workflow implemented in their system uses different tools for addressing each part of the process, from identifying which part of the input article is a bibliographic reference to the extraction of reference metadata. Finally, he shows a demo of the tool using a PDF available online as input.

Eric, from Iowa State University, shows some early results analysing the availability of reference data in OpenAlex. He created a Jupyter notebook that describes the work and makes it reproducible. He highlights some statistics about the number of references included in the analysed papers and shows, among other things, that there are some papers with no references included in OpenAlex that have them defined in the source article. The Jupyter notebook also includes useful graphs to look at the entire dataset, as well as a single DOI, in time.

George, from the University of Strathclyde, introduces Rioxx (the Research Output Metadata Schema), a tool that was originally devised as an OAI-PMH metadata application profile that many repositories in the UK have supported. Currently, the Schema is maintained by the UK Confederation of Open Research and Repositories and has a governance group that works to improve it. Version 3 Release Candidate has recently been made available and reuses existing vocabularies such as Dublin Core and Schema.org. It allows the identification of publication types and other relations with different expressions of the same work (such as preprint, PDF and XML versions, etc.) and other related objects (such as dataset, code, projects and grants).

In her video, Dominika, from Crossref, talks about the importance of metadata matching, that is matching string referring to something (such as an affiliation or a paper) to an existing entity that can be identified by a PID. For instance, at Crossref, 70% of bibliographic references included in article metadata sent by the publishers do not contain the DOI of the cited work. They were able to retrieve it automatically for only 41% of these references. Then, she ends the speech by answering some relevant questions: do we need less and less matching in time? Is title lookup enough for matching citations? Can we be sure that all citation links in the data are correct? Concluding: the metadata matching is not perfect, but it is very much needed.

Dietrich, from the ZB MED Information Centre for Life Sciences, introduces NFDI, a German initiative to build a national research data infrastructure. Among the chapters of this initiative, one is dedicated to NFDI 4 Data Science, which focuses on supporting all steps of the complex and interdisciplinary research data lifecycle, including collecting/creating, processing, analysing, publishing, archiving, and reusing resources in Data Science and Artificial Intelligence. The speech is structured by answering four questions that introduce NFDI 4 Data Science, FAIR Digital Objects, and reproducibility.

Kim, from the Fraunhofer Institute for Applied Information Technology, starts her speech by highlighting how inefficient it is to transfer entire scholarly data from one container to another and even how difficult it is to exchange only the "right" and relevant data instead of all of them. Then, she moves to push the need for a distributed architecture for data exchange and briefly discusses how the F of the FAIR principles (that is Findability) can be implemented within such an architecture. She concludes with a question: does a distributed architecture also need a distributed PID system?

Last but not least, Bianca, from Sesame Open Science, shows that funders' metadata in Crossref are available for only 25% of articles but explains it is hard to assess if an article has been supported by some funds or not. In order to analyse this, she ran a study with 5 thousand NWO-funded articles available in Crossref and discovered that only 65% have funding information in Crossref. This image differs publisher by publisher since some publishers deposit this information for several of their articles (for instance, the American Chemical Society) but others do not (such as the Cambridge University Press). Other bibliographic databases, though, contain more funding information than Crossref, probably because they extract it from the acknowledgement section of the articles.